

SARS-CoV-2 is Wolbachia for humans

SARS-CoV-2 may constitute the evolution of an additional switching layer over human phenotypes, as a response to the overshoot of homo sapiens, in a transposition of the kind of evolved population-level action, over the entire class Insecta, we see in wolbachia.

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We call SARS-CoV-2 Wolbachia for humans, not in a literal sense, but in the top-down sense:

Wolbachia is a bacterial symbiont across roughly half all insects.

It can directly functionally change aspects of insect phenotypes, including their sex. In these senses, it is quite different from SARS-CoV-2, and indeed any virus.

What we wish to call attention to here is not the mechanism of wolbachia on individual organisms, but playing out across populations.

We are describing an equivalence between the changes wolbachia negotiates between an extremely numerous, distributed, and differentiated whole class of species, and the environment.

This equivalence is meant in the sense that wolbachia seems to be acting as an additional switching layer over intra- and inter-species phenotypes, across 50% of a globally distributed class of species.

SARS-CoV-2 has special properties which seem to be self-optimising for acting as such a switching layer, over the homo sapiens species:

1. SARS-CoV-2 fragilises the organs, immune systems, and neurology of a percentage of cases
2. This fragilisation is mostly silent: more asymptomatic cases have

been fragilised than there are symptomatic cases

3. SARS-CoV-2 spreads rapidly and asymptotically, evading detection unless adequate randomised testing is in place

[source](#)

These properties combine into a primer for synergistic risk, not only immediately renegotiating the balance between an extremely numerous, distributed, and differentiated species and the environment, but setting up a persistent new layer for further renegotiations.

SARS-CoV-2 literally requires a new layer of coordination of heterophily and homophily among individuals and groups [1].

[1] [Social influence and interaction bias can drive emergent behavioural specialization and modular social networks across systems](#)

It deeply breaks-up pre-existing boundary conditions of social behavior and reproduction.

It is causing more vulnerable and less-developed populations to withdraw into defensive authoritarian modes [2].

[2] [Pathogens and Politics: Further Evidence That Parasite Prevalence Predicts Authoritarianism](#)

It coincides with the artificial introduction of wolbachia-carrying strains of mosquitos in Sri Lanka and other dengue, Zika, and similar virus hotspots [3].

[3] [Wolbachia and dengue virus infection in the mosquito *Aedes fluviatilis*](#)

Interestingly, homo sapiens doesn't (yet) require a bacterial symbiote to fluidise sexual phenotype. This fundamental aspect of the new switching layer seems to have emerged primarily as a rapid cultural evolution in the generations after X.

While it would seem to make all the sense in the world right now for a naturally-occurring biological agent to selectively target the Y chromosome, something more interesting is happening.

As per E.O. Wilson, humans transpose the evolved design of insect colonies to much larger scale. But where class Insecta needed a bacterial endosymbiont

(Wolbachia) to manage overproduction of males, an evolutionary mechanism for this is emerging in homo sapiens *culturally*.

This is a stunning example of biology transposing evolutionary mechanisms from matter (wars and other forms of literal androicide) to information (human polysexuality).

If we understand Gaia scientifically:

Making Evolutionary Sense of Gaia

- [article](#)
- [PDF](#)

Could this pandemic usher in evolution's next major transition?

- [article](#)
- [PDF](#)

.. then not only can SARS-CoV-2 defensibly be said to be Gaia protecting herself, but the emergence of polysexual culture can be framed as an aspect of the evolutionary transition described in the second reference above. Restated:

Gaia is protecting herself by fluidising human sexuality *through human culture*, without the need for a viral or bacterial agent

Human polysexuality is emerging as a cultural adaptation renegotiating the relationship of an extremely numerous, distributed, and differentiated species with the biosphere.

This renegotiation is itself occurring over a medium that 'recapitulates evolutionary biology as a medium that allows for continual integrated adaptations across local-global scales' [[source](#)], the open internet and web.